

Legendre polynomial modelling-based permutation entropy to analyse encrypted Time series

* Meryem Jabloun, * Nacim Ramdani,, and **Andreas Panayides

*PRISME Laboratory, Université d'Orléans
12 rue de Blois, 45067 Orléans, France. ** 3AHealth compagny, E902 95, Strovolos
2020,Nicosia,Cyprus.

Abstract. Securing sensitive data, particularly healthcare information transmitted through cloud services, is mandatory. However, preserving the privacy of medical data during analysis poses a significant challenge. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to develop tools capable of evaluating the robustness of encryption techniques and determining the level of confidence in privacy preservation.

This paper presents a comparative analysis between two entropy measures: Legendre polynomial modelling-based permutation entropy (LPPE), recently introduced in [1] as a complexity measure for time series, and established variants of permutation entropy (PE), such as multiscale PE (MPE) [2] and phase PE (PPE). The study focuses on their application to encrypted data as indicators of privacy preservation.

State-of-the-art Information entropy can serve as a quantitative measure to assess the disorder or randomness in data. While few entropy-based methods have been utilised to evaluate the resilience, efficacy, or vulnerability of encryption techniques [3,4,2,5,6,7,8], they are less commonly employed to detect corrupted or compromised data [3,4,2,5,6,7,8].

The Shannon entropy (SE) is the most commonly employed entropy for assessing encryption robustness, with a high SE value serving as a relevant indicator of a secure encryption technique. Recently, entropies based on ordinal pattern theory, such as PE and its variants MPE [2], have emerged as alternative metrics for this purpose. However, there has been limited discussion in the literature regarding the application of the newest PE variants, namely PPE and LPPE, as indicators of encryption robustness.

Methods PE is a concept that applies the SE to the probability distribution of ordinal patterns (OP) extracted from the data, rather than the original data. An OP represents the permutation in the increasing order of segments of successive samples. Classical PE, MPE and PPE, unfortunately, exhibit sensitivity to factors such as sampling frequency, noise presence and downsampling preprocessing. In contrast, the recently introduced LPPE benefits from applying SE to the probability distribution of OP constructed using a robust Legendre

polynomial fitting of the sample segments. LPPE demonstrates superior performance compared to PE, MPE and PPE, making it a promising candidate for evaluating encryption robustness.

Results and conclusion We conduct an analysis of homomorphically encrypted data* using the complexity measures: PE, MPE, PPE and LPPE. Preliminary results depicted in fig. 1, 2 and 3 indicate that LPPE performs better than PE as an indicator of well-performed encryption on these data. Other medical datasets will be considered to consolidate our findings.

Keywords: Encrypted data, multiscale permutation entropy, phase permutation entropy, Legendre polynomial modelling.

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<https://huggingface.co/spaces/zama-fhe>

	Original	FHE +Identity	FHE+Blur	FHE+ W&B	Decrypted
PE	0.8689	0.9157			0.8044
LPPE	0.3822	0.3862			0.4710
PE	0.8689		0.7163		0.7352
LPPE	0.3822		0.3841		0.3795
PE	0.8689			0.9041	0.8713
LPPE	0.3862			0.3863	0.3809

Table 1. LPPE with scale $L=15$ and OP of length $d = 5$ versus PE with $d = 5$ applied to images depicted in fig. 1.

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Fig. 1. Data analysed using PE and LPPE in Table 1: (left column) Original data, (middle column) Fully homomorphical Encryption followed by filtering, from top the bottom: Blur filter, white and black threshold, identity filter and (right column) decrypted data.

Fig. 2. Data analysed using PE (0.7481, 0.9185, and 0.7481) and LPPE (0.3575, 0.3875, and 0.3575) from left to right side, respectively. Both PE and LPPE are calculated using $d=5$ and the LPPE segments are set to $L=15$.

Fig. 3. Gaussian noise analysed using PE (0.9717, 0.8469, and 0.9717) and LPPE with (0.7341, 0.6526, and 0.7341) from left to right side, respectively. Both PE and LPPE are calculated using $d=5$ and the LPPE segments are set equal to $L=15$.

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